

A Restaurant that Provides Fast and Courteous Service

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ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
04 June 2026

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KEYWORDS: hospitality, service quality, fast service, polite service, customer experience, customer loyalty, fast food restaurant

ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze how restaurants provide fast and courteous service to customers from a hospitality perspective and to understand customer experiences with the quality of service provided. The study uses a qualitative approach with descriptive methods to gain a deep understanding of customer experiences, perceptions, and expectations of restaurant service. Data collection techniques were carried out through observation, in-depth interviews, and documentation. Research informants consisted of customers and restaurant employees selected using a purposive sampling technique based on their experience and involvement in restaurant service activities. Data analysis was conducted using an interactive analysis model that includes data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. The results show that service speed, politeness, friendliness, and employee responsiveness are the main factors influencing customer satisfaction and emotional experiences. Customers feel more comfortable, appreciated, and have a higher tendency to revisit when receiving fast and courteous service. In addition, the quality of interpersonal interactions between customers and employees has been shown to play a significant role in shaping customer loyalty to the restaurant. This study provides a theoretical contribution to the development of hospitality and service quality studies through a qualitative approach and provides practical implications for restaurant managers in improving service quality and customer experience.

I. INTRODUCTION

The restaurant industry is a crucial sector within the hospitality industry, experiencing rapid growth in line with the growing public demand for fast, convenient, and high-quality food service. Increasing competition means restaurants are demanding not only good food but also prompt and courteous service. In the service industry, service quality is a key factor influencing customer satisfaction, loyalty, and the decision to revisit a restaurant. Fast service reflects a restaurant's operational efficiency, while courteous service demonstrates the employee's ability to build positive interpersonal relationships with customers. Therefore, restaurants that provide prompt and courteous service tend to have a positive image among consumers and maintain their competitiveness.

The concept of hospitality in restaurants extends beyond food presentation to encompass the overall customer experience. Modern customers increasingly pay attention to how they are treated by restaurant staff, including their attentiveness, responsiveness, communication, and

responsiveness to customer needs. Research by Rajput & Gahfoor (2020) shows that restaurant service quality has a positive relationship with customer satisfaction and intention to revisit fast food restaurants. In addition, the study confirms that good service is an important factor in retaining customers in the highly competitive restaurant industry.

Several previous studies have also revealed that service speed is a crucial dimension of restaurant service quality. Kendur et al. (2020) examined the service quality of fast-food restaurants, explaining that factors such as service speed, employee compassion, and environmental cleanliness are key elements influencing customer satisfaction and consumer behavior. Horax & Sanjaya (2017) demonstrated that fast-food restaurant customers place a high value on employee response time, as this is related to time efficiency and customer convenience when purchasing food.

In the hospitality context, polite service is also a crucial aspect because it can create a positive emotional experience for customers. A friendly, polite, and empathetic attitude

from restaurant employees can enhance customer perceptions of service quality. Research by Greve (2014) demonstrated that service quality and restaurant atmosphere significantly influence customer satisfaction at fast-casual restaurants in Germany. These findings suggest that interpersonal interactions between customers and restaurant employees are crucial in creating a pleasant dining experience.

In Indonesia, the development of fast food restaurants and modern restaurants has also shown significant growth. Competition between restaurants forces companies to continuously improve service quality to retain customers. Research by Kristiawan et al. (2021) found that service quality has a direct influence on customer satisfaction at fast food restaurants in the Greater Jakarta area. The study confirmed that customers who receive good service are more likely to revisit and recommend the restaurant to others.

Although numerous studies have been conducted on restaurant service quality, most previous research has used a quantitative approach, focusing on the relationship between variables such as service quality, customer satisfaction, and revisit intention. Meanwhile, research using a qualitative approach to in-depth explore customer experiences with fast and courteous service in restaurants is still relatively limited. However, a qualitative approach can provide a more comprehensive understanding of customer perceptions, experiences, and expectations regarding restaurant service quality.

Based on this phenomenon, this study aims to analyze in-depth how restaurants provide fast and courteous service to customers and how customers interpret this service experience from a hospitality perspective. This research is expected to provide theoretical contributions to the development of hospitality and service quality studies, while also providing practical benefits for restaurant managers in improving service quality and customer experience.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Quality is a key factor determining the success of the restaurant industry, particularly fast-food and modern restaurants, which rely heavily on the speed and quality of customer interactions. From a hospitality perspective, fast and courteous service not only serves to meet customer needs functionally but also creates a positive emotional experience during the consumption process. The concept of service quality generally refers to a company's ability to meet customer expectations through the dimensions of reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles. Research by Bilqis et al. (2025) on restaurant service quality continues to evolve due to changing consumer behavior, which increasingly demands service efficiency as well as a comfortable and enjoyable experience.

Research conducted by Mathe-Soulek et al. (2015) explains that speed of service, employee involvement, cleanliness, and order accuracy are the main factors influencing customer satisfaction in fast-food restaurants. This study used a mixed-methods approach and found that friendliness and speed of service are important restaurant dimensions in shaping fast-food customer loyalty. These findings indicate that customers assess not only food quality but also the quality of the service interactions they receive during their stay at the restaurant. Furthermore, research by Mendocilla et al. (2026) revealed that service quality in fast food restaurants has a significant influence on customer satisfaction and loyalty. This integrative study highlights that responsiveness and interpersonal communication are crucial elements in building a positive customer experience in modern fast food restaurants. The study also emphasizes the importance of employee training to improve the ability to provide polite and responsive service to customers.

Another study by Amoozegar et al. (2025) on the use of the SERVQUAL model in the Malaysian restaurant industry showed that the dimensions of responsiveness, assurance, and empathy significantly influence customer satisfaction in fast-food restaurants. The study found that customers tend to be satisfied when restaurant employees provide fast, polite, and attentive service. Furthermore, service quality has also been shown to increase customer trust in the restaurant. In the South African context, a study by Basera et al. (2025) explained that service quality and food quality are key determinants of customer satisfaction and behavioral intentions in fast-food restaurants. The study showed that customers are more likely to return to a restaurant if they receive fast, friendly, and professional service from restaurant employees. These findings reinforce the importance of hospitality service in creating a positive customer experience.

A study by Mendocilla et al. (2021) developed the QUICKSERV instrument as a service quality measurement tool specifically for fast-food restaurants. The study found that the dimensions of responsiveness, courtesy, and assurance are key indicators of service quality in fast-food restaurants. This study shows that fast and polite service can improve customer perceptions of restaurant professionalism and strengthen customer loyalty in the long term. Research by Sandika et al. (2020) on fast food restaurants in Indonesia found that service quality, convenience, and food quality significantly influence customer satisfaction. The study explained that Indonesian customers place a high value on compassion and speed of service when determining their satisfaction with fast food restaurants. This finding suggests that a friendly service culture is a crucial characteristic in the Indonesian hospitality industry.

Based on the various previous studies mentioned above, it can be concluded that fast and courteous service is a crucial element in increasing customer satisfaction,

behavioral intentions, and customer loyalty in the industry. However, most previous research has been dominated by quantitative approaches that focus on the relationships between variables. Therefore, this study attempts to contribute through a qualitative approach to a deeper understanding of customer experiences with fast and courteous service from a hospitality perspective.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses a qualitative approach with descriptive methods to deeply understand how restaurants provide fast and courteous service to customers from a hospitality perspective. A qualitative approach was chosen because this study aims to directly explore customers' experiences, perceptions, and meanings regarding restaurant service quality. According to Creswell & Creswell (2018), qualitative research allows researchers to gain a comprehensive understanding of social phenomena through direct interaction with participants and the research environment.

The research locations were several fast food restaurants and modern restaurants characterized by fast and customer-oriented service. The research locations were selected using a purposive sampling technique, considering restaurants with high customer traffic, fast service systems, and direct service interactions between employees and customers. The research informants consisted of restaurant customers and restaurant employees selected using a purposive sampling technique based on their experience in restaurant service activities. Customer informants were selected based on having visited at least twice, while employee informants were selected based on their direct involvement in the customer service process.

Data collection techniques included observation, in-depth interviews, and documentation. Observations were conducted to directly observe the restaurant's service process, from welcoming customers and ordering food, serving food, and interactions between employees and customers. In-depth interviews were conducted in a semi-structured manner so researchers could explore customers' experiences, perceptions, and expectations regarding the restaurant's prompt and courteous service. Furthermore, documentation in the form of photographs, field notes, and other supporting data was used to strengthen the research findings.

The primary instrument in this study was the researcher herself (the human instrument), who played a role in collecting, interpreting, and analyzing the research data. To assist in the data collection process, researchers used interview guidelines, a voice recorder, and observation notes. Interview questions focused on aspects of service speed, employee compassion, responsiveness to customer needs, service comfort, and customer experience during their time at the restaurant.

The data analysis technique used the interactive analysis model from Miles et al. (2014), which consists of three stages: data reduction, data presentation, and conclusions. Data reduction was carried out by selecting and connecting interview and observation data according to the research focus. Next, the data was presented in descriptive narrative form to facilitate interpretation of the research results. The final stage was drawing compelling conclusions based on patterns, themes, and relationships among data discovered during the research.

To maintain data validity, this study employed source and method triangulation techniques. Source triangulation was conducted by comparing information from customers and restaurant employees, while method triangulation was conducted by comparing the results of observations, interviews, and documentation. Thus, the data obtained is expected to have a high level of credibility and accuracy, enabling a comprehensive description of the phenomenon of fast and courteous service in the restaurant industry.

IV. RESULT

Customer Perceptions of Restaurant Service Speed

Research results indicate that most customers consider service speed to be a key factor in determining the quality of their restaurant experience. Based on observations and in-depth interviews with customers, customers have high expectations for service efficiency, particularly in the food ordering process, menu presentation, and employee responsiveness to customer requests. Customers perceive restaurants that provide fast service as demonstrating professionalism and strong operational readiness in serving customers.

During field observations, researchers found that restaurants with an organized service system tend to shorten customer wait times. Customers expressed that short wait times provide a sense of comfort, especially for customers visiting during work breaks or when the restaurant is busy. Most customers stated that fast service relates not only to food presentation but also includes the speed with which employees greet customers, take orders, provide menu information, and complete payment transactions.

Interview results also indicate that customers are highly sensitive to service delays. When service is slow, customers tend to feel dissatisfied and experience a decrease in satisfaction with the restaurant. Some customers expressed that service delays cause emotional discomfort, especially when the restaurant appears unable to manage customer queues effectively. In some situations, customers even compare service experiences between restaurants before deciding whether to revisit.

Research has found that the use of technology such as digital ordering systems and electronic payments helps improve restaurant service efficiency. Restaurants that use digital systems tend to reduce order errors and expedite the

service process. Customers perceive that the integration of technology into service provides a more practical, modern, and efficient experience. From a hospitality perspective, speed of service is seen as a restaurant's respect for customers' time. Customers assume that restaurants that provide prompt service demonstrate attention to their needs. Therefore, speed of service is a key indicator influencing customer perceptions of a restaurant's overall service quality.

Employee Courtesy and Friendliness in Building Customer Experiences

Research results indicate that employee courtesy and compassion play a crucial role in building positive customer experiences in restaurants. Based on in-depth interviews, customers considered friendly attitudes, polite communication, and the ability of employees to provide attentive service to customers to be factors that influence customer comfort during their stay at the restaurant. Most customers stated that interpersonal interactions between customers and employees had a significant emotional impact on their dining experience. Customers felt more comfortable when greeted with smiles, greetings, and polite communication from restaurant employees. This friendly attitude created a warmer atmosphere and enhanced customers' perceptions of the restaurant's professionalism.

Observations showed that employees with good communication skills tended to build positive relationships with customers more easily. Employees who were responsive to customer questions, politely provided menu recommendations, and demonstrated empathy for customer needs were considered to contribute significantly to customer satisfaction. Furthermore, customers appreciated employees who maintained a positive expression even when the restaurant was busy.

This study also found that customers pay close attention to employees' body language and nonverbal expressions during the service process. Eye contact, tone of voice, and promptness in assisting customers are crucial in building perceptions of service quality. Customers perceive polite service as reflecting a restaurant's hospitality-oriented work culture. Conversely, customers report that unfriendly or inconsiderate employee behavior can detract from the restaurant's overall image. Negative service experiences are even more memorable for customers than the quality of the food served. Therefore, politeness and compassion are crucial elements in fostering customer loyalty to a restaurant.

Employee Responsibility to Customer Needs

Research results indicate that employee responsibility is a critical dimension of restaurant service quality. Responsiveness, in this study, refers to employees' ability to provide prompt, accurate, and appropriate assistance to customers' needs throughout the service process. Interviews revealed that customers felt satisfied when employees

responded quickly to customer requests without having to wait too long. Customers perceived employees' responsiveness to customer needs as a reflection of the restaurant's readiness to provide high-quality service. This responsiveness was evident in employees' ability to handle changes to orders, answer customer questions, and resolve customer complaints professionally.

Field observations indicate that restaurants with high levels of responsiveness tend to have good coordination between employees. Employees are seen helping each other expedite the service process, especially when the restaurant is busy. Customers perceive that good coordination between employees provides a more efficient and comfortable service experience. This study also found that customers highly value employees who proactively assist customers before they raise a complaint. For example, employees who promptly clear tables, offer additional items, or provide information related to orders are perceived as demonstrating a high level of customer care. These proactive actions enhance customers' perceptions of the restaurant's hospitality quality.

However, the study found that a lack of staff during peak hours is a factor that hinders responsible service. In some situations, customers have to wait longer due to limited manpower and high customer numbers. This demonstrates that restaurant operational management has a significant impact on the effectiveness of customer service.

Customers' Emotional Experiences of Restaurant Service

Research results show that prompt and courteous service not only functionally influences customer satisfaction but also emotionally impacts their restaurant experience. Customers expressed that positive service experiences create feelings of comfort, appreciation, and attention from the restaurant. Most customers stated that a friendly and responsive service atmosphere made them feel more relaxed while enjoying their meal at the restaurant. Customers assumed that good service improved their mood and provided a more enjoyable dining experience. In some cases, customers even linked the service experience to their emotional state during their visit to the restaurant.

Interview results also indicated that customers' emotional experiences were influenced by the quality of communication between employees and customers. Customers felt more satisfied when employees demonstrated empathy and attention to their needs. This empathy fostered a closer interpersonal connection with the restaurant. The study found that customers tended to remember service experiences more than the physical aspects of the restaurant. Customers more readily remembered how they were treated by employees than the restaurant's decor or amenities. Therefore, emotional experiences are a crucial factor in shaping customer perceptions of restaurant hospitality quality. Furthermore, customers who experienced positive

emotional experiences were more likely to revisit and recommend the restaurant to others. This shows that restaurant service has a big influence on the formation of customer loyalty through positive emotional experiences.

Customer Loyalty as an Impact of Prompt and Courteous Service

Research results show that prompt and courteous service has a significant influence on restaurant customer loyalty. Customers who experience positive service are more likely to return to the restaurant and recommend it to family and friends. Interviews revealed that service quality is a key consideration in determining their decision to revisit. While food quality remains important, customers believe that the service experience plays a greater role in creating a positive impression of a restaurant. Customers prefer restaurants that provide friendly, prompt, and consistent service over those that simply offer good food.

The study also found that customer loyalty is formed through the accumulation of positive experiences during interactions with the restaurant. Customers who consistently receive good service demonstrate a higher level of trust in the restaurant. They feel confident that the restaurant will meet their expectations on each visit. Furthermore, loyal customers tend to voluntarily promote the restaurant through word-of-mouth. Satisfied customers often share their positive experiences through social media or direct recommendations within their community. This suggests that prompt and courteous service not only increases customer loyalty but also helps enhance the restaurant's image broadly.

However, research has found that customer loyalty can decline if restaurants fail to maintain consistent service. Customers have high expectations of restaurant service standards, so even small changes in service quality can influence a customer's decision to return. Therefore, restaurants need to maintain consistent service quality to maintain long-term customer loyalty.

V. DISCUSSION

Service Speed as a Key Factor in Customer Satisfaction

The results of this study indicate that service speed has a significant influence on restaurant customer satisfaction. This finding demonstrates that modern customers are highly time-efficient, making fast service a crucial part of their dining experience. From a hospitality perspective, service speed reflects a restaurant's ability to manage operations effectively and optimally meet customer expectations. This study's findings align with research by Ryu et al. (2008), which explains that efficient service quality has a direct influence on customer satisfaction and behavioral intentions in the restaurant industry. This study indicates that restaurant customers tend to assess the quality of their experience based on the restaurant's ability to provide prompt and accurate service.

This study also supports research by Li et al. (2012), which found that service efficiency is a key indicator in shaping restaurant customers' perceived value. This study demonstrated that customers who receive prompt service tend to report higher levels of satisfaction than customers who experience delayed service. Furthermore, research by Min & Min (1997) indicates that customer wait time is closely related to customer satisfaction levels at fast food restaurants. When customers have to wait too long, their perception of the restaurant's quality decreases. These findings strengthen the results of this study that service efficiency is an important determinant in retaining customers.

In the context of modern restaurants, the use of digital technology has also been shown to increase service speed. This finding supports research by Morosan & DeFranco (2016), which explains that the application of service technology in the hospitality industry can improve operational efficiency and the quality of the customer experience. Therefore, restaurants need to integrate service technology with operational systems to enhance customer satisfaction.

Service Courtesy and the Formation of the Hospitality Experience

The study showed that employee courtesy and compassion significantly influence the customer experience during their stay at a restaurant. This finding confirms that hospitality is not only related to the food product, but also the quality of interpersonal interactions between customers and restaurant employees. This study's findings align with research by Choi & Kandampully (2019), which explains that emotional service interactions have a significant influence on customer trust and loyalty in the restaurant industry. Customers who receive friendly and courteous service tend to develop a stronger emotional connection with the restaurant.

This research also supports the findings of Yen & Tang (2019), who found that employee friendliness is a key factor in creating a memorable dining experience. The study explained that customers more easily remember the interpersonal treatment they receive than the physical aspects of the restaurant. Furthermore, research by Liu & Jang (2009) showed that the quality of interpersonal communication between customers and employees in a restaurant significantly influences customer satisfaction. The polite, empathetic, and friendly attitude of employees helps create a more comfortable and enjoyable dining atmosphere. The results of this study also reinforce the hospitality concept developed by Lashley (2008), which emphasizes that the core of hospitality lies in the service organization's ability to create positive social relationships with customers. Therefore, polite service is a crucial element in building a restaurant's image and maintaining customer loyalty.

Service Responsiveness from a Service Quality Perspective

This study found that employee responsibility is one of the main dimensions influencing customer perceptions of restaurant service quality. Responsiveness relates not only to the speed of service but also to the employee's ability to understand and meet customer needs appropriately. This finding aligns with Parasuraman et al.'s (1988) SERVQUAL concept, which explains that responsiveness is a key dimension in assessing service quality. Customers tend to be satisfied when employees are able to provide prompt and professional assistance. Research by Qin & Prybutok (2009) also shows that responsiveness has a significant influence on customer satisfaction in the fast food restaurant industry. The study explained that customers value responsive service more than the physical attributes of the restaurant.

Furthermore, research by Namkung & Jang (2007) found that employees' ability to promptly address customer needs contributes to increased behavioral intentions among restaurant customers. Customers who feel cared for tend to have a higher intention to revisit. The results of this study also support research by Han and Hyun (2017), which explains that service responsiveness has a positive relationship with customer emotional satisfaction in the hospitality industry. Therefore, restaurants need to improve employee training to enable them to provide fast, accurate, and professional responses to customers.

Customer Emotional Experiences in the Restaurant Industry

Research results show that fast and courteous service can create positive emotional experiences for restaurant customers. Customers not only evaluate restaurants based on product quality but also on how they are treated during the service process. These findings align with research by Walls et al. (2011), which explains that customer experiences in the hospitality industry are strongly influenced by emotional interactions between customers and service providers. Positive emotional experiences increase customer satisfaction and loyalty to the restaurant.

Research by Jang & Namkung (2009) also shows that customer emotional responses significantly influence revisit intentions in the restaurant industry. Customers who feel comfortable and valued are more likely to revisit a restaurant. Furthermore, research by Ali et al. (2016) found that emotional hospitality experiences are a crucial factor in shaping customer satisfaction and loyalty. In the context of this research, fast and courteous service helps create a pleasant emotional experience for customers. These research findings reinforce the experiential marketing theory developed by Schmitt (1999), which explains that customer emotional experiences are a crucial part of creating consumption value. Therefore, restaurants need to build a service strategy that focuses not only on efficiency, but also on the customer's emotional experience.

Customer Loyalty as a Result of Service Quality

Research results show that fast and courteous service significantly contributes to the formation of restaurant customer loyalty. Customer loyalty is formed through consistent and ongoing positive service experiences. This finding aligns with research by Kandampully and Suhartanto (2000), which explains that service quality has a direct relationship to customer loyalty in the hospitality industry. Customers who experience positive service tend to have a stronger commitment to the restaurant. Research by Han & Ryu (2009) also shows that customer satisfaction and emotional attachment are important mediators in the formation of restaurant customer loyalty. Customers who are satisfied and have an emotional connection with a restaurant are more likely to have repeat visits. Furthermore, research by Choi & Kim (2013) found that service quality has a significant influence on word-of-mouth communication among restaurant customers. Satisfied customers not only revisit but also voluntarily recommend the restaurant to others. These research findings also support research by Ryu et al. (2008), which explains that restaurant service quality is a key factor in shaping customer behavioral loyalty. Thus, restaurants need to maintain consistent fast and polite service in order to maintain customer loyalty in the long term.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study shows that prompt and courteous service is a crucial factor in creating good restaurant service quality from a hospitality perspective. Service speed is not only related to a restaurant's operational efficiency but also reflects the restaurant's ability to respect customers' time and effectively meet their needs. Customers tend to experience higher levels of satisfaction when restaurants provide fast, accurate, and responsive service throughout the dining process. Furthermore, employee courtesy and disrespect have been shown to significantly impact customers' emotional experiences. Friendly demeanor, polite communication, attentiveness, and empathy can create a comfortable and enjoyable service atmosphere. This study found that customers recall interpersonal experiences more readily than the physical aspects of a restaurant, making the quality of interactions between customers and employees a key element in building a positive restaurant image.

The study also shows that service responsibility is crucial in enhancing customer perceptions of restaurant hospitality quality. Employees who respond quickly and are perceived as professional can enhance customer comfort and satisfaction. Conversely, delays in service and inattention to customers can diminish the overall quality of the customer experience. This study found that prompt and courteous service has a positive emotional impact on customers, such as feelings of appreciation, comfort, and attention during their time at the restaurant. These emotional experiences

contribute to the formation of customer loyalty, including the intention to revisit and recommend the restaurant to others. Therefore, restaurant service quality not only influences short-term customer satisfaction but also impacts the long-term sustainability of the restaurant business.

Theoretically, this research contributes to the development of hospitality and service quality studies through a qualitative approach that provides a more in-depth description of the customer experience. This research also demonstrates that the dimensions of service speed, courtesy, compassion, and responsiveness are crucial components in building the customer experience in the modern restaurant industry.

Based on the research findings, restaurant managers are advised to improve service quality through regular employee training on interpersonal communication, hospitality, and customer service. This training is crucial for enhancing employees' ability to provide prompt, courteous, and professional service to customers. Furthermore, restaurants need to build a work culture oriented toward customer satisfaction to maintain consistent service quality. Restaurants are also advised to improve operational efficiency through the use of technology services such as digital ordering systems, electronic payments, and customer queue management. The use of technology can help speed up the service process, reduce order errors, and enhance customer experience.

Furthermore, restaurant management needs to pay attention to the number and distribution of employees, especially during peak hours, to ensure optimal service delivery. Adequate staffing will help restaurants provide faster service and reduce customer waiting times. Furthermore, regular service evaluations through customer satisfaction surveys are necessary to identify service weaknesses that need improvement. For future researchers, it is recommended to develop research on restaurant service quality using a mixed-methods or quantitative approach to more broadly measure the relationships between variables. Future research could also expand the research object to various types of restaurants, such as fine dining restaurants, cafés, or traditional restaurants, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of hospitality practices in the restaurant industry.

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